

Eleven years of leading photography projects for Wikipedia

0. Information about this document

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Abstract: The document summarizes eleven years of experience of Mr. Jan Lochman in managing and administering grant projects supporting volunteers in documentary photography for Wikipedia. In 2019, Mr. Lochman was successful in his grant application for a project to photograph production processes and acquire scientific photographs at the Wikimedia Foundation. After a year, Wikimedia Czech Republic consolidated the project with another documentation project into the larger Mediagrant project, which ensured the supply of photographs of Czech settlements, protected areas, monuments, ponds and waterways, industrial processes and events to Wikipedia for the next ten years.

Thanks to this work, Mr. Lochman became familiar with managing volunteer processes, assessing grant calls, creating grant applications, and the basics of accounting and IT project management. The experience gained from uploading photos to the Wikimedia Commons repository and reviewing volunteers' work led him to conclude that photography is an essential carrier of information. Therefore, every country should have its own repository of freely available photographs of places and events. Some countries, such as Poland or Hungary, have such repositories; others do not. At the end of this document, Mr. Lochman offers guidance on accessing such a repository.

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1. Introduction

The goal of this document is to describe 11 years of experience of Mr. Jan Lochman leading and administering projects on photographic documentation for Wikipedia. What he has learnt and what recommendations he could provide for similar projects. This report is Mr. Lochman's personal view.

2. Towards leading projects

Mr. Lochman began editing Wikipedia in 2005 and, three years later, cofounded Wikimedia Czech Republic, a voluntary association that aims to support Wikipedia and disseminate free knowledge. These actions brought him into the Wikimedia movement, where he was not just editing articles on Wikipedia but also contributing to other projects such as Wiktionary¹ and Wikiversity² as well as uploading photographs to Wikimedia Commons – the central file repository for Wikipedia and Wikidata.³

3. Scientific and Specialized Photographs Project

When the Wikimedia Foundation invited the Wikimedia Czech Republic association to submit project proposals, Mr. Lochman remembered that he had visited various scientific and industrial facilities during his studies at the university and that there were no similar photos on Wikipedia. Therefore, he came up with the idea of providing similar images for Wikipedia.

His project proposal, called *the Scientific and Specialized Photographs Project* (hereinafter, SSPP), was first successful in the association's selection process and then in the Wikimedia Foundation's narrow selection process, and received a one-year 1100 USD grant.

4. Project outcomes and continuation

In the first project run during 2009–2010, the team visited three production facilities and two institutions. It documented their processes and/or collections.⁴

This first experience showed that processing photos in this way is time-consuming, and it is better to focus on photographing whole groups and processing them at once.

The Scientific and Specialized Photography Project became a valuable learning pilot, whose focus Mr. Lochman narrowed in the subsequent years.⁵ In contrast, the other one – *Photo of Czech Municipalities Project* (hereinafter, POCMP)⁶ became an excellent model project, ready to

1 A sister project of Wikipedia, aiming to collect all lexemes and provide information on them.

2 Another Wikipedia sister project aiming to create open educational resources and provide a place for open research.

3 Secondary database from Wikimedia Family. Sister project of Wikipedia.

4 Granted project report:

https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:PEG/WM_CZ/Acquiring_scientific_and_specialized_pictures/Report.

5 Interestingly, around the time Mr. Lochman decided to discontinue the “Scientific Photography” component in our project, a similar initiative called Art Library (in Czech, Knihovna umění) emerged independently in another organization, focusing on collecting and sharing artistic photographs. The project Art Library worked on a similar mechanism to our collection of scientific photographs and thus shows us, as a project that broadened Wikipedia with hundreds of specific pictures, a potential way to work in this direction.

6 Report of the Photo of Czech Municipalities Project:

https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:PEG/WM_CZ/Czech_Municipalities_Photos/Report.

reproduce. The Wikimedia Foundation subsequently enabled the continuation of both projects. They merged into one large project within which other photography topics emerged: either copying Photos of Czech Municipalities, thus making the work easier and allowing more photographers to participate, or building on the experience of SSPP and focusing on specific topics, providing valuable photos from fewer volunteers.

Mr. Lochman added simpler projects, copying POCMP, focused on Bodies of Water and Events.

5. Eleven years as a professional administrator

The consolidated projects were called Mediagrant and regularly received grants from the Wikimedia Foundation until 2021, when Wikimedia Czech Republic canceled them.

As part of a more professional approach, the organisation had created an elected three-member supervisory and management body. The original project leaders became expert assistants for individual topics and part of the Grant Committee (Fig. 1). At the same time, a Wikimedia Czech Republic volunteer programmed a tracking tool that monitored individual requests for reimbursement, photographed objects, and the status of processing.

Mr. Lochman then administered his topics for eleven years by creating documentation, motivating volunteers, assessing their requests for reimbursement, and recording the benefits of the projects. Over time, he began to administer other topics due to a smaller number of administrators or the complete departure of administrators. These included the topics Photos of Czech Municipalities and Protected Areas.

During ten years, 23 volunteers have created more than 15,000 photographs in topics administered by Mr. Lochman.⁷

Figure 1: Organisation structure of Mediagrant

⁷ It would be better to record the number of newly improved Wikipedia articles with photos. However, due to the later removal of specific categories that would allow such a calculation, this is not possible. For such a calculation, Mr. Lochman should calculate it programmatically. That is not within the time available to create this informative document. Therefore, we provide at least a link to the historical statistics in Czech: https://cs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedista:Juandev/Statistika_Mediagrantu.

6. Reflection on problems and shaping the environment

6.1. Challenging metadata creation

6.1.1. Current practice

Taking and processing photos is not as time-consuming as creating appropriate metadata and categorizing them. In the case of Wikimedia Commons (hereinafter, Commons), the photographer does most of the work manually (Fig. 2).

Each photo on Commons has a unique title that should include the object's geographical location and its specifications. It also consists of an unstructured description, with a complete sentence that explains what is in the photo and where it was taken. Some editors insert this description in two or three languages, often English plus their native language. Most photos also have coordinates, which the uploading tool extracts from the EXIF and inserts into the metadata section on the website. However, many photographers do not have a camera that automatically writes geographical coordinates to EXIF, so they add them manually.

Figure 2: An example of what a curator has to do when uploading a photo to Wikimedia Commons. Green highlights what can be easily automated

Last but not least, each photo must be classified into at least one category. The categories are only in English, which makes it difficult for curators who do not speak English perfectly. It is classified by geographical location and by the predominant subjects depicted in the photo into at least one, and more often several, categories. If a given category does not exist, it needs to be created and correctly included in the category tree.

There is no single, simple procedure for finding the relevant category, so each curator approaches the problem differently. Some enter a string into the search and wait for the results. Another moves to a category where they expect to find it and browses the category tree. Others search the English Wikipedia, which has more articles and therefore more links to Commons' categories. If someone does not speak English at all, they try to click from a general term on the Wikipedia of their native language to the English Wikipedia, then search for the appropriate category on Commons based on the images in the article.

The optional field also includes a structured description of the photo. A structured description can also be in several languages and is shorter than an unstructured one, but very similar in its expression. Another optional fields become structured data.

6.1.2. Processing in batches and problems with professional photography

Themes that followed on from POCMP, such as Bodies of Water or Protected Areas, began to be processed in their entirety. We found that photographers of settlements were still unable to identify all the objects in their photographs, nor could they do so in a reasonable time. Although there was pressure to do so, it turned out that dedicating a special route to each subject (topic) was better. That is, one route is purely behind the settlements, and it takes documentary photographs of the settlements and categorizes all photos into the given settlement's category. If the Wikipedia editor who wrote an article about a given village needs photos, they themselves know which photos show a school or a church. They can even describe and categorize them in more detail. In the same village, someone can document only the monuments and, when subsequently processed on Commons, categorize previously uploaded photos of someone else.

However, in the case of Specialized Photography and similar topics, the problem was that this simplification could not be done from the beginning, because each photo featured a different significant subject or part of a process; therefore, the curator had to describe and categorize it separately. Here, it turned out that volunteers did not enjoy doing a single photo tour, taking hundreds of photos in specific categories, and then describing and categorizing them for months. Sometimes it resulted in not uploading the photographs from the documentary journey to Wikimedia Commons at all.

6.1.3. Simplification and technical solution proposal

Based on these findings, demand for Specialized Photography has gradually decreased. Industrial production photos have been missing from Wikipedia articles, so it is better to upload at least some photographs than to require processing all the photos taken.

Thanks to his own photography and curatorial activities, as well as topic management and work with volunteers, Jan Lochman then designed the Describator system⁸, which should speed up the work of all documenters on Wikimedia Commons through various programmatic solutions. The basic requirement of the system is that the photographer should enter information about the photo only once, and the system will automatically reproduce it in various formats. This system would drastically simplify the procedure described in Chapter 6.1.1. The goal should be for documenters to document, not sit for long hours at the computer. What can be automated should be automated.

6.1.4. VicuñaUploader involvement

Part of Mr. Lochman's comprehensive work in the photographic project, in addition to system analyses and solution proposals, was also an intervention to ensure the possibility of uploading. The second most widespread method for uploading the VicuñaUploader (VU) software stopped working after some time and had no maintainer. Thus, Mr. Lochman intervened to keep it alive, found a developer to fix the VU, secured him a grant, and led the project.⁹

⁸ See Describator system proposal: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/User:Juandev/Describator/en>.

⁹ See VicuñaUploader grant proposal page: https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:Project/Rapid/Juandev/Accessibility_and_improvement_of_Vicu%C3%B1aUploader.

6.2. Demotivation

Another valuable insight was how to work with volunteers. Excessive strictness proved demotivating, and it was necessary to change the approach so that the evaluation was very open from the beginning, with recommendations added later on how the person should improve their documentary style.

6.3. Individual vs. community photography

Last but not least, it turned out that although the project's performance was quite decent - for example, the Photo of Czech Municipalities project documented almost 80% of all settlement units - individual participants did not enjoy documenting the countryside and municipalities alone. That is why user Aktron and Mr. Lochman organized the first multi-day joint trip to the Czech-Polish border region in 2016 and received grants for it from both the Wikimedia Czech Republic and Wikimedia Poland.¹⁰ Aktron brought knowledge from the Wikiexpedition he participated in Poland, and Mr. Lochman from his own travels and analyses of individual photography within Czech projects.

The result was four more Wikiexpeditions in the Czech Republic and Poland, organized by Mr. Lochman with grant funds from Wikimedia Poland and the Wikimedia Foundation. It took place annually between 2017 and 2022. These events, as modified by Mr. Lochman, underwent changes from drive-through to area photography, with the possibility of returning to the given location to photograph the unphotographed.

Mr. Lochman prepared maps of unphotographed villages, which he manually sorted by the number and quality of photos available on Wikimedia Commons, and the participants followed these maps. This method of preparing materials for Wikiexpeditions was more accurate than the recommended Wikidata query, which ignored unsuitable or poor-quality photographs.

6.3.1. Problems and solutions of Wikiexpeditions

The main issue with Wikiexpeditions was that participants took a long time to upload photographs and add them to Wikipedia.

Therefore, Mr. Lochman explored various solutions until his team determined that the best approach was to use a film clapper and a list of objects that each participant had photographed. This method allowed the participants to process the photos even after a long time, when they had forgotten where each village began and ended in a long line of images on their SD card. In practice, the photographer would take a picture of their hand or foot between each settlement. This divided the dataset of photos into segments that corresponded to a handwritten list the photographer created along the way (Fig. 3), recording the photographed settlements.

Figure 3: Improve photo of the paper on which the photographers recorded the order in which they photographed the villages and the abbreviations of the names of the photographers who photographed the village

¹⁰ Overview of the project: https://cs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedie:Wikiexpedice/2016/Wikiexpedice_Slezsko/en.

Later, we shortened the time for taking photos during the day on the expedition so that some participants could process everything in the afternoon. Some processed the photographs during the expedition itself, while others did so within a few weeks. It was a significant shift from the beginning, when some participants processed photos only after many urgencies, or did not upload them at all.

7. Decline of photographic projects

After a few years, the association's new leadership came in. It pushed for the creation of a new project in which volunteers would take just one photo for each item on Wikidata. The original documentary project for Wikipedia had to merge with the new one. Nevertheless, Mediagrant continued for a few more years.

However, changes to the originally quite well-designed system began to complicate the work. The tracker function was redesigned, and categories were merged on Wikimedia Commons. These changes helped the new project, but some things were harder to control in the old projects, and Mediagrant's Topic managers could no longer do statistical evaluations as before.

With the advent of COVID-19 in 2020, Mr. Lochman left his position as a professional administrator after eleven years. The project continued for another year before being canceled.

8. Recommendations for documentary projects based on volunteerism

8.1. Uneven situation within individual countries

A central digital repository of documentary photographs is lacking in some countries. In the Czech Republic, the Czech News Agency has an extensive general documentary photo database. However, due to its status, photographs are not free of charge, and searching the database is not easy.¹¹

Things are better in Germany, for example, where the German Federal Archives,¹² which was established in 1952, shares its photographs under free licenses. Similarly, in other countries, historical documentary photographs are freely available thanks to private projects such as Fotopolska¹³ in Poland and Fortepan¹⁴ in Hungary.

8.2. Software and long-term commitment to preserve

Each country should build a collection of historical images to connect the past with the present. The problem with such an archive is, of course, its technical complexity and the requirements for long-term storage and backup. The entity establishing such an archive should be aware of the long-term commitment it will have to make; however, examples such as Fotopolska and Fortepan show that it is possible to implement them on a private basis.¹⁵

11 See the database: <https://www.profimedia.cz/>.

12 German Federal Archives website: <https://www.bundesarchiv.de/en/federal-archives/>.

13 Fotopolska website: <https://fotopolska.eu/>.

14 Fortepan website: <https://fortepan.hu/>.

15 Both projects have been operating for 15 years.

Backing the database up can be partially addressed by opening the archive under free licenses, which will ensure that some images and their metadata are harvested and stored by other collectors.

As for the software, Mr. Lochman can recommend MediaWiki, the same software Wikimedia Commons uses. Or something better can be developed that takes into account not only editors who edit image metadata one by one, but also those who edit them once for a package of images.

Mr. Lochman also recommends generating a SHA hash for each photo, which will save future users time by making it easy to check whether a picture is already in the repository when uploading a new one. The current Wikimedia Commons does not support this feature natively.

Last but not least, the new project could use structured categories built on a simplified model or tree. That would combine the positive features of both current Wikimedia Commons models.

8.3. Community care

One way is to let volunteers build a documentation project. Even if there is no enthusiastic community, the founder can attract collaborators by slowly building the database itself and advertising it.

Another option could be to verify Lochman's hypothesis of connected communities,¹⁶ and invite other communities that photographically document particular objects to place their photos in this project.

Of course, the repository operator can also offer ready-made lists and maps of objects that need to be photographed, and it is good to pay close attention to the community and newcomers and support them.

9. Conclusions

Over eleven years of leading photographic projects, our volunteers built an extensive, high-quality documentation base that has contributed to long-term content development and secured stable support from the Wikimedia Foundation. The project strengthened the reputation of photographic activities, produced methodologies applicable beyond its own scope, and demonstrated sustainability in an international context.

Over time, several key insights emerged. The project confirmed how sensitive volunteer work is to communication style, team culture, and the overall level of social trust within the environment. It also demonstrated that stable processes, supportive leadership, and a clear structure are crucial for maintaining long-term motivation. Another important insight is that photography functions primarily as a carrier of information: its documentary value may remain high even when technically imperfect, as long as essential visual information remains readable. The experience further showed that institutional support and understanding of project goals strongly influence whether recruitment strategies or methodological innovations can be effectively implemented.

¹⁶ This hypothesis is based on the idea that communities of interest documenting a particular area can benefit from placing their photos in a central database, where the central database community will edit their metadata and their photos will be more visible. At the same time, the central database will come across more photos. For many documentation communities and individual projects, the goal is not to make money from documentation, but to share it with people.

Although the goal of significantly expanding the editor community was not fully achieved, the limiting factors were mainly systemic and institutional rather than operational. The knowledge Mr. Lochman gained in team leadership, grant management, documentation practices, and intercultural communication provides a solid foundation for future initiatives in environments with stronger institutional support and higher social trust.